

The Ethics of the Algorithmic Prediction of Goal of Care Preferences: From Theory to Practice

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are quickly gaining ground in healthcare and clinical decision-making. However, it is still unclear in what way AI can or should support decision-making that is based on incapacitated patients' values and goals of care, which often requires clinician and surrogate decision-makers' inputs. Although the use of algorithms to predict patients' most likely preferred treatment has been discussed in the bioethics literature, no example has been realized in clinical practice. This is due, arguably, to the lack of a structured approach to the epistemological, ethical, and pragmatic challenges arising from the design and use of such algorithms. The present paper offers a new perspective on the problem by suggesting that preference predicting AI be viewed as socio-technical systems with distinctive life cycles. We explore how both known and novel challenges map onto the different stages of development, highlighting interdisciplinary strategies for their resolution.

Keywords: algorithms; clinical ethics; artificial intelligence; decision-making;

goal concordant care; patient preferences

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Introduction

In clinical settings, preference-sensitive decisions regarding diagnostic and treatment options often need to be determined when patients are incapacitated and unable to make such choices for themselves. Advance directives, which allow patients to declare preferences regarding future care while still competent, are often lacking or inconclusive. In such cases, surrogate decision makers help establish what the patient would have presumably wanted. Ideally, their insight into the patient's preferences along with clinicians' expertise come together in a process of shared decision-making that aims to define the best possible treatment for the patient. However, effectively determining what is in the patient's best interest in accordance with their values and goals on their behalf can be challenging in practice.

This is especially true in the case of severe and unexpected events that necessitate timely intensive care interventions. In these situations, providing goal-concordant care, i.e., care that corresponds to patient preferences, requires clarity around whether patients would prefer palliative approaches or lifesaving interventions depending on the likelihood and extent of cognitive or motor deficits, survival rates, and the burden of the treatment itself. Clinicians must balance a range of ethically challenging and complex demands, including providing treatment consistent with the patient's presumed preferences and values, supporting the patient's family and loved ones, ensuring timely decision-making, and overseeing the clinical care (Rid and Wendler 2010). However, as the literature has shown, there is often a considerable gap between the care that is received and the care patients would have wanted (Kiker et al. 2021; Rutz Voumard et al. 2021). Moreover, available instruments to record goal of care preferences, such as advance directives, still do not provide the guidance clinicians often need to identify patient preferences (Yadav et al. 2017; Sudore et al. 2018).

Moreover, surrogates tend to be part of the decision-making process. However, research has shown that surrogates are often limited in their ability to accurately predict their loved ones' preferred care (Spalding 2021; Buchanan, E, and Brock 1989) and often suffer emotional distress in the face of such decision making (Rid and Wendler 2010).

Researchers have proposed to address the aforementioned challenges by designing and implementing algorithms that would compute the most likely preferred treatment of the incapacitated patient (Biller-Andorno and Biller 2019; Biller-Andorno et al. 2021; Rid and Wendler 2014b). To the best of our knowledge, the first of these proposals dates back to 2010, when Rid and Wendler introduced the idea of using patients' socio-demographic data to predict preferred treatment options (Rid and Wendler 2010). Since 2010, other algorithmic proposals have been made: they all share the idea that algorithms can learn patterns in data that correlate individual-level information to preferred treatments for a variety of clinical scenarios. Despite preliminary evidence suggesting that patients, surrogates, and clinicians may respond positively to the use of these algorithms in clinical practice (Biller-Andorno et al. 2021; Wendler et al. 2016; Howard et al. 2021) and the successful use of artificial intelligence methods in other medical applications (Nagendran et al. 2020), a decade after Rid and Wendler's proposal, no working example of systems to predict patient's preferences in clinical practice has yet emerged.

The reasons, we argue, are manifold. First, the idea of using algorithms to predict patient's preferred treatments is fraught with theoretical challenges that pertain to epistemology and ethics. Some of these challenges relate to patient autonomy (Jardas, Wasserman, and Wendler 2021; Sharadin 2018), the difficulty of avoiding bias, and the importance of addressing explainability given the "black box" nature of many AI algorithms (Biller-Andorno and Biller 2019). Second, the design, development, and use

of these algorithms need to address pragmatic challenges, such as safety, reliability, and adequate testing to foster usability and receptivity among clinicians (Petersen et al. 2021). Lastly, the literature mostly addresses the aforementioned theoretical and pragmatic challenges separately, missing the opportunity to promote a more comprehensive discussion that considers the relationship between the two and would be better positioned to address such interdisciplinary concerns.

The goal of the present paper is to support both the design of algorithms to predict patient preferences and their implementation in clinical practice by centring questions of ethics and considering a *life cycle* perspective of the clinical AI systems in which these algorithms ought to be embedded. This view moves away from the existing algorithm-centred perspective, instead recognizing that AI in clinical applications is more than an algorithm and a data flow: it is a system interacting with stakeholders according to the different stages of its life cycle embedded in a particular sociotechnical context (van de Poel 2020). Focusing on the particularities of all stages of the AI system life cycle, the aim is to capture the relevant interactions with stakeholders without limiting the discussion exclusively to the challenges stemming either from conceptualization (e.g., data collection) or from the integration in clinical decision-making (e.g., during the possible interactions with surrogates). In fact, we consider the *before*, the *during* and the *after* of the AI system use in clinical practice and the relation between these phases. To do so, we break down the life cycle of the clinical AI system in five sequential steps, highlighting theoretical and pragmatic challenges sequentially. To guide our exposition, we focus on a use case of relevance for goal-concordant care, namely decision-making in the intensive care unit (ICU). However, the proposed approach can be generalized to other use cases of clinical relevance, such as incapacitation in the case of Alzheimer's disease.

The main contributions of our approach are the following. First, it allows us to map systematically existing epistemological, ethical, and pragmatic challenges, such as the necessity to respect patient autonomy, or to promote appropriate explanations of the predicted treatments, into the different steps of the AI system life cycle. Second, it allows us to identify and discuss novel challenges arising from the use of clinical AI systems to predict patient's preferences, such as those emerging from the update of data collection procedures because of retrospective critical care agreements studies. Finally, it provides actionable recommendations to support the design and use of these systems in agreement with normative design requirements. As a result, we argue, our approach could promote an interdisciplinary dialogue between ethicists, clinicians, and computer scientists focusing on the still-standing challenges that arise from the AI-assisted prediction of patient preferences and finally enabling the integration of such systems into clinical practice.

The plan of the paper is as follows. In Section 1, we introduce a clinical use case that will guide our discussions throughout the paper. In Section 2, we discuss the current state of debate on algorithmic prediction of patient preferences. In Section 3, we introduce our approach. We then present our conclusions.

1. A Use Case for Predicting Patient Preferences: Decision-Making in the ICU

Decisions in the ICU must be made quickly due to the severity of the quickly evolving clinical presentation and the time-sensitive nature of many of the interventions. Additionally, in the ICU, patients are often incapacitated, such as in the case of haemorrhagic stroke, and cannot directly consent to or refuse interventions. While

clinicians primarily seek to follow the will of the patient, including in the form of respect for any existing advance directive, input may be needed from surrogate decision-makers and healthcare professionals if the patient is incapacitated and an advance directive is either not available or not readily applicable to the presenting scenario.

De facto, ethical, institutional, social and pragmatic constraints, such as time pressure and whether there is any indication of relevant care preferences, may influence which treatments are administered and hamper clinicians' efforts to provide patient-centered, goal-concordant care, especially during a pandemic. The above specificities make the ICU a paradigmatic case where methods of evidence-based shared decision-making can be implemented and where well-considered innovation can have significant impact on the quality of care (Hoffmann, Montori, and Del Mar 2014).

Advance directives, a form through which users leave written instructions outlining their future health care preferences, play an important role in determining care for incapacitated patients. Although research has shown that patients desire advance directives (Emanuel et al. 1991; Schiff, Rajkumar, and Bulpitt 2000), and that surrogate decision-makers find them helpful (Baker et al. 2000; Kolarik et al. 2002), their completion rate is generally low (Yadav et al. 2017). Moreover, advance directives have significant shortcomings, such as content that can be difficult to understand and limited applicability to the concerns of certain ethnic and social groups (Sudore et al. 2018). Finally, advance directives may be unavailable when needed, even if completed, or may fail to provide relevant guidance for the scenario at hand (Austin et al. 2015).

If an incapacitated patient does not have an advance directive, then surrogate decision-makers need to identify the presumed will of the patient drawing on past conversations or comparable life choices. However, literature shows that surrogate

decision-makers have a limited ability to accurately predict the goal of care preferences of their loved ones (Spalding 2021; Buchanan, E, and Brock 1989; Shalowitz, Garrett-Mayer, and Wendler 2006). Moreover, making such life and death decisions for another often generates significant emotional distress (Pochard et al. 2005; Rid and Wendler 2010). Additionally, surrogates often lack guidance from ICU clinicians in how to serve their role (Cunningham et al. 2018). Finally, surrogate decision-makers may not be available for consultation when needed, leaving the burden of deciding whether or not to pursue certain treatments to clinicians.

In the remainder of this paper, we will use the decision-making in the ICU as a use case to clarify our discussions on the prediction of patients' preferred treatments with the use of technology. However, our considerations apply to other clinical settings, such as the emergency and palliative care unit, and can be generalized to other scenarios of incapacitation, such as in the case of Alzheimer's disease.

2. Algorithm-Aided Prediction of Patient Preferences

In light of the difficulties arising from the shortcomings of advance directives and the limitations of surrogate decision makers, researchers have suggested the potential value of designing algorithms that predict patients' most likely preferences to support clinical decision-making that involves incompetent or incapacitated patients (Biller-Andorno and Biller 2019; Biller-Andorno et al. 2021; Rid and Wendler 2010; 2014a; 2014b).² Rid and Wendler's patient preference predictor (PPP) is an early example of such an algorithm (Rid and Wendler 2010). Once fed on appropriate data,

²In this context, an algorithm is a set of—deterministic or probabilistic—rules run by computer systems to predict an output of interest, given input data.

the algorithms would compute a preferred treatment for a pre-selected variety of clinical interventions. More recent contributions suggest the use of AI rather than algorithms that use a pre-defined set of criteria,³ projecting use cases such as a Do-Not-Attempt-to-Resuscitate Predictor (Biller-Andorno et al. 2021). As input data, demographic information that influences care preferences, such as age, gender, marital status, health condition and previous healthcare experiences, could be gathered alongside more general aspects of the person's known goals and values to produce either a population-based or individual-based prediction. In addition, the large volume of data traces on the internet and on social media would provide ample material for a self-learning AI.

The working hypothesis states that an *accurate* algorithm increases the chance that patients receive treatment consistent with their preferences (Jardas, Wasserman, and Wendler 2021). Therefore, the use of AI methods, such as machine learning, may be preferred, as they have proven to deliver high performance in multiple clinical use cases (Nagendran et al. 2020). High-performing AI-based algorithms have the potential to reduce surrogate decision-makers' distress. Moreover, it could support clinicians in augmenting decision-making (Lamanna and Byrne 2018) by aiding them in incorporating patients' values and preferences into considerations in an evidence-based rather than anecdotal way (Hoffmann, Montori, and Del Mar 2014).

³ An example is the population-based rule stating that *any* incapacitated patient will prefer life-saving treatment “when there is at least a 1% chance, following the intervention, that the patient will reach a health state which includes the ability to reason, remember, and communicate” (Shalowitz, Garrett-Mayer, and Wendler 2007). Recently, Meier et al. (Meier et al. 2022) introduced an example of “algorithmic advisor” to support decision-making on morally sensitive cases. The algorithm predicts the most likely intervention, based on historical cases brought before clinical ethics committees (Meier et al. 2022).

However, although preliminary studies show that clinicians, patients and surrogate decision-makers are in favour of the introduction of algorithms to support decision-making (Biller-Andorno et al. 2021; Howard et al. 2021; Wendler et al. 2016), and despite the increasing use of AI in healthcare (Nagendran et al. 2020), no such algorithm has been integrated into clinical practice.

Actually, the proposal of using algorithms to predict patient preferences is not free from criticism pointing to unresolved theoretical and practical challenges. However, the former, which pertain to the epistemology and ethics of algorithms, rarely inform the latter, which discuss limitations in the design and possible use of algorithms in clinical practice. For example, some authors highlight the necessity of tackling bias in data collection; promoting the use of methods to increase explainability of opaque AI algorithms; and providing transparent, secure, and reliable infrastructure for their use (Biller-Andorno and Biller 2019). Others focus on ethical challenges, highlighting how such algorithms could potentially endanger patient autonomy and the importance of addressing the perceived acceptability of such tools on the part of patients, surrogates, and clinicians (Sharadin 2018; Rid and Wendler 2014a; John 2018). These criticisms emphasize the role of patients and their families as decision-makers, as opposed to algorithms. They also discuss the problem of limiting freedom of choice by using demographic data as predictors of preferred treatments, among others (Sharadin 2018; John 2018). Despite recent efforts (Jardas, Wasserman, and Wendler 2021), these challenges remain largely unaddressed.

In summary, these discussions capture some of the limitations stemming from algorithmic predictions of patient preferences, with and without AI. Attention typically centers on *the* algorithm and its input-output data flows at *specific* stages. This perspective, however, falls short by neglecting exploration of the socio-technical

context of such a decision support system at *all* stages of its use. An alternative approach would support researchers in responsibly closing the gap between conceptualization and actual use in clinical practice, providing a structure for discourse around epistemological, ethical, and pragmatic challenges and subsequent strategies of resolutions. We defend this proposal in the forthcoming sections.

3. Algorithms to Predict Patient Preferences: A Roadmap to Implementation

3.1 Clinical AIs as Socio-Technical Systems

A socio-technical system is the result of a technical artefact, e.g., a computer system, human agents interacting with it, and the specification of social norms or rules that regulate the interactions (van de Poel 2020). A clinical AI that predicts patient preferences is an example of socio-technical system: the technical artifact, i.e., a computer system, generates the suggested treatments and interacts with a set of human agents (e.g., patients, clinicians, nurses, and surrogates), from within the set of social norms specified by the procedures and goals of shared decision-making. In particular, these norms inform a series of normative requirements deemed necessary for the acceptance and use of AI in clinical practice (Floridi 2019). Examples include safety, robustness, reliability, privacy, security, transparency, explainability, algorithmic fairness, and non-discrimination (Petersen et al. 2021).

In Section 2, we have shown that the algorithm-and data flow-centred debate on predicting patient preferences has stimulated noteworthy research efforts. Still, the articulated theoretical considerations have not yet informed the development of such algorithms or their testing in empirical studies. Vice versa, technical system requirements are not discussed through the lens of epistemology and ethics beyond high-level proposals (Biller-Andorno and Biller 2019) or discussions are limited to

specific topics, such as the design of surveys for data collection (Rid and Wendler 2014a).

In summary, we argue that this siloed approach falls short of appropriately capturing the complexity of the problem at hand. Therefore, our proposal is to leverage this complexity by promoting a structured discourse that holds a clinical AI preference predictor as a socio-technical system that evolves over time. By definition, this means considering the technical artefact (i.e., the clinical AI of which the evolving algorithm for preference predictions is a part), user interactions, and the social institutions at each relevant point of time within the system life cycle—see (Lemonne 2018) for a simplified example. To do so, we model the system life cycle as a sequence of five steps: 1) data collection, 2) modeling, 3) system design, 4) deployment, and 5) evaluation. These are presented in Figure 1.⁴ At each life cycle step, we highlight theoretical and pragmatic challenges and discuss the relevant interactions with stakeholders, including the use of additional digital tools to support them. The normative requirements for clinical AIs (Petersen et al. 2021) underline all steps of the AI system life cycle.

Following this approach, we can map the challenges discussed in the literature, such as respecting patient autonomy or fostering the explainability of predictions, into different steps of the AI life cycle, and, therefore, discuss step-specific strategies for resolution. Moreover, the discussion of the steps of the AI life cycle supports the identification of new challenges that designers, ethicists, and clinicians need to address. As a result, our approach provides a theory-driven, yet application-oriented, roadmap to the implementation of AI systems to predict patient preferences in clinical practice. We

⁴ For the sake of readability, we avoid showing the feedback loops between the different life cycle phases, such as from “Modeling” to “Data Collection”, that may occur in practice.

collect the steps, their corresponding challenges, and our recommendations in Figure 2. These are discussed in detail in the forthcoming sections.

Figure 1. The AI system life cycle. At each step, we highlight the main theoretical and pragmatic challenges. The normative requirements for clinical AIs underline all steps of the life cycle.

3.2.1 Data Collection

Collecting treatment scenarios. When surveying for treatment preferences, the following dimensions must be weighed against one another: the burden of treatment, i.e. the hardship endured while being treated; the outcome, i.e., the health state and length of life after the treatment; and the likelihood of any such outcome (Fried, Bradley, and Towle 2002). Given this complexity, the number of questions needed to capture someone’s preferences represents a challenge for data collection. For example, Rid and Wendler suggest 110-130 questions that may cover 10-20 treatment scenarios (Rid and Wendler 2014b), which is, arguably, a rather intensive exercise for any respondent.⁵

⁵ Although reviews have shown, for example, that the average number of daily medical ICU interventions per patient is in the hundreds (Donchin et al. 1995).

Few studies have explored the validity of instruments for eliciting input to determine preferred treatments. One example, the WALT instrument, does so in fewer questions, considering multiple aspects of treatment preferences while presenting only six clinical scenarios (Fried, Bradley, and Towle 2002). Wendler et al.'s study (Wendler et al. 2016) puts forward only a single-scenario questionnaire in which respondents express their preferences in the case of lost mental capacity due to a car accident. It is still uncertain what is necessary and sufficient for such tools to capture the respondent's position well. In summary, a key step in generating data that preference predicting algorithms could use is to successfully manage the complexity of the variables involved: clinically relevant granularity must be captured, but the number of variables and scenarios should not overwhelm the respondent or interpreter.

One solution we suggest would be to fix an outcome for each treatment of interest and ask respondents to indicate the minimum or maximum likelihood of an outcome at which they would consent to treatment and, where relevant, for what minimum duration following. For example, respondents may be asked to indicate the maximum likelihood of severe cognitive impairment following cardio-pulmonary resuscitation they would accept and still desire resuscitation or the minimum number of years of survival following an invasive procedure that would be necessary for them to desire the treatment. Respondents could indicate their choices through a simple sliding scale on a digital interface. The benefit of this approach is that it would allow for the collection of responses regarding a higher number of treatments and outcomes and,

therefore, generate a fine-grained understanding of highly individualized perspectives on future health scenarios.⁶

A meaningful way to then refine an understanding of the respondent's position would be to compliment such sliding scales with ranking questions where respondents prioritize general goals of care and indicate the relative importance of certain personal values. This can become a reference point to better understand the profile of decision makers and serves as another valuable input for making judgements when the elicited scenario does not directly correspond to the real-life clinical scenario that presents. It could also function as a reflection point, enriching respondents' consideration of their choices, and possibly serve to validate the consistency of their stated preferences with their stated goals and values.

Bias in future-self forecasting. In the context of predicting patients' preferred treatments, designers must address a peculiar source of bias: the one that emerges in the very act of declaring preferences. Research shows that biases distort people's ability to accurately recall past experiences and realistically forecast future scenarios, leading to errors in decision making (Gilbert, Gill, and Wilson 2002; J. Halpern and Arnold 2008). Even competent patients with high levels of health literacy often have difficulty realistically anticipating how they would respond to future disability (Ditto, Hawkins, and Pizarro 2005; Gilbert, Gill, and Wilson 2002; J. Halpern and Arnold 2008). The main example is impact bias (Wilson and Gilbert 2013), produced by focalism, i.e., focusing excessively on what is lost (e.g., as a consequence of a disability), and by

⁶ The AI would then compute the likelihoods for each treatment and outcome. See Section 3.2.2 for more details on modeling.

immune neglect, i.e., the underestimation of coping strategies (Gilbert et al. 1998). As a result, people are poor safeguards of their future well-being: their biases affect the formation of realistic beliefs about their future quality of life and lower their ability to make meaningful and accurate preference predictions. Preferences tend to evolve over time, affected by one's physical and psychological condition. Although studies have explored mitigating such bias in medical decision-making (Almashat et al. 2008), more research is needed to develop methods for assessing and managing bias in predicting future-self preferences (Ditto, Hawkins, and Pizarro 2005). The same is true for further decisional challenges such as deciding under conditions of uncertainty and probabilistic thinking.

To address these limitations, researchers have advocated for the use of technology to improve people's decisional capacity when completing advance directives (Austin et al. 2015; Biller-Andorno and Biller 2021; Green and Levi 2012). Existing efforts include multimedia tools (Hickman et al. 2014), low-health-literacy multi-language printouts (Braun, Karel, and Zir 2006), and "e-planning" solutions, i.e., web-based applications (Austin et al. 2015; Sudore et al. 2018). Some authors have recently remarked that, more broadly, digital technologies have the potential to aid informed decision-making by supporting the four components necessary for decisional capacity (Biller-Andorno, Gloeckler, and Ferrario 2021): understanding, appreciation, reasoning, and communication (Appelbaum and Grisso 1988). Arguably, these technologies could improve users' ability to vividly project themselves into future healthcare scenarios and facilitate the process of updating goal of care preferences over time as the individual herself changes (Biller-Andorno, Gloeckler, and Ferrario 2021). A digital tool that aids decision-making could potentially improve the quality of responses by enhancing the user's ability to future forecast, leading to a more likely hypothetical picture of the

respondents future care goals and preferences (Biller-Andorno, Gloeckler, and Ferrario 2021). Even if biases and other challenges were not completely eliminated, a significant improvement as compared to the status quo would—in the absence of other disadvantages—be enough to justify the use of AI-based advance decision-support.

3.2.2 Modeling

Multiplicity in modeling. An open question is the number of machine learning (ML) models required to implement an AI to predict patient preferences. The literature does not investigate this point, instead referring to “the” algorithm that would predict preferences (Rid and Wendler 2014b). However, the specificities of data collection and ML modeling suggest a more complex picture. In fact, designers would need to train one ML model per treatment scenario, either to classify the likelihood of agreeing with the proposed treatment in the scenario or to compute the maximum (or minimum) likelihood of outcome that would make the patient consent to the proposed treatment (see Section 3.2.1). This results in the maintenance of tens of ML pipelines, each one possibly characterized by different modeling procedures. As a result, this represents a notable investment in resources that proponents of AIs to predict patient preferences must consider. To solve this challenge, designers may try reducing the number of treatment scenarios to be collected depending on the different levels of ML model performance, aggregating “contiguous” scenarios while preserving clinical relevance,⁷ or ranking them and then repeating the modeling procedures. As a result, AI would predict only a selection of all possible treatments yet retain its relevance for shared decision-making and system manageability across the different steps of its life cycle.

⁷ Such as those describing the same treatment and outcome, but different (e.g., “high”, “medium”, and “low”) likelihoods or durations.

Technical bias and transparency. The technical choices that designers make during modeling are—yet another—potential source of bias. Bias can be introduced through the choice of ML models, the selection of performance measures, and the methodologies to reduce class imbalance in data, i.e., the presence of an unequal distribution of classes (e.g. “intervention: yes” and “intervention:no”) per each treatment scenario.⁸ These design choices may be dictated by theoretical reasons, such as different accuracy-complexity trade-offs (London 2019), or pragmatic reasons, such as regulatory requirements. As a result, it becomes necessary to align the implementation of technical choices with the epistemic and ethical expectations of AIs. To do so, designers can draw on recent accounts of AI transparency, such as “design transparency” (Loi, Ferrario, and Viganò 2020), that support the disclosure of “the standards, norms, and goal that were implemented in the system” (Loi, Ferrario, and Viganò 2020), how those norms were translated into technical requirements, the choice of performance measures, and the consistency of these choices throughout model retraining.

Explainability in modeling. Without appropriate “epistemic guarantees” during ML modeling, clinicians may feel compelled to thoroughly validate each AI prediction during decision-making, undermining the benefits and feasibility of AI support. Relatedly, clinicians may be concerned that they must accept the opacity of the algorithms, accept an inability to satisfactorily trace the justification for the given

⁸ For example, during data collection (see Section 3.2.1), only 2% of respondents could agree on undergoing cardio-pulmonary resuscitation procedures in the case of a high risk of cognitive deficit and low likelihood of survivability. Class imbalance seems reasonable in presence of particularly unfavourable treatment scenarios.

suggestion. The challenge posed by explainability emerges at multiple stages: when data scientists and clinicians aim to validate the ML models through an understanding of the underlying logic of outcomes; when they assess performance; and when they identify patterns, including errors. Although explainability has been evoked as a requirement for algorithms that predict patient preference (Biller-Andorno and Biller 2019; Biller-Andorno et al. 2021), no explicit recommendations have been made.

Here, we propose a two-step approach to address the need for explainability during “Modeling”. First, as the overall input needed for training a preference predictor model is relatively small compared to other deep learning use cases in healthcare (Nagendran et al. 2020), designers should start by training models that are interpretable by design. Examples include generalized additive methods and decision trees (Markus, Kors, and Rijnbeek 2021). Second, while testing more complex models to improve performance and better capture patterns in data, they should rely on methods such as Shapley values (Lundberg and Lee 2017) to compute feature importance scores and provide a degree of protection against spurious correlations. Moreover, they should use post-hoc interpretability methods, such as counterfactual explanations (Wachter, Mittelstadt, and Russell 2018), to explain any given conclusion. Counterfactuals elucidate a suggestion (i.e., avoid subjecting the patient to a certain procedure) by providing an alternative scenario that describes the conditions under which the alternative prediction would have emerged. Counterfactuals are algorithmically easy to generate and similar to how clinicians often communicate (Barocas, Selbst, and Raghavan 2020). For example, in the ICU, a counterfactual may explain the suggestion against the placement of a shunt to drain cerebrospinal fluid in a 67 year-old incapacitated patient that would have a 90% likelihood of leading to moderate cognitive disability:

“If the patient had been 60 years old and the likelihood of moderate cognitive disability 75%, then he might likely have chosen shunt placement instead of palliative care, ceteris paribus”

However, although explanations, such as counterfactuals, are a valuable tool in the “Modeling” step of the AI system, they are neither necessary nor sufficient to justify the ethically sound use of AI, foster trust in it, and increase its acceptance rates (Bjerring and Busch 2020; Durán and Jongsma 2021; Ferrario and Loi 2022). Therefore, designers should consider their use only in addition to extensive performance evaluation of the AI and its empirical testing with stakeholders.

Performance evaluation: AI vs. surrogates. In the “Modeling” step, the accuracy of such AI is tested against the baseline of surrogates’ performance in predicting preferences of their loved ones. The importance of this comparison is often emphasized in the literature on algorithmic prediction of patient preferences (Rid and Wendler 2010; 2014b; 2014a): in fact, the key assumption is that a high performing AI will better promote goal concordant care than surrogate decision-makers. However, this assumption must be tested with appropriate methods. Surrogates may have limited knowledge of the patient’s preferences; their perceptions of the patient’s values and goals may be biased; and the knowledge they do have may not reflect the specificities of the situation at hand. Thus, surrogates may be guided by salient memories and their own life chronicle perspective, which are shaped by repeated interactions with other family members, and consultations with additional stakeholders (Shapiro 2019).

In summary, surrogates’ predictions are the result of the accrual of disparate information over time in processes that cannot be *a priori* modelled or appropriately elicited in a laboratory setting (Shapiro 2019). Therefore, we argue, the epistemic value of an AI vs. surrogates performance comparison is to provide a *prima facie* evidence of

the accuracy of the algorithm and should not be overestimated. It should be complemented by other performance assessment routines (see Section 3.2.5) and allow informing refinements of the “Data collection” and “Modeling” steps based on surrogates’ feedback and decision-making procedures.

3.2.3 System Design

Embedding values in system design. The lack of a structured body of human-computer interaction (HCI) research specific for AI systems, especially for clinical applications (Dove et al. 2017; Gillies et al. 2016), affects the development of an AI to predict patient preferences. AI systems often fail to move to practice since clinicians are reluctant to use them despite good *in-vitro* performance (Elwyn et al. 2013; Jaspers et al. 2011). Moreover, when implemented in clinical practice, the subpar integration of these systems into the workflow impedes clinician motivation to use them (Sittig et al. 2008). Yang et al. refer to this challenge as a “lack of contextual integration” (Yang, Steinfeld, and Zimmerman 2019). To this end, in line with our approach, they advocate for a socio-technical-aware design of clinical AIs supporting decision-making that would reflect the values of stakeholders, the workplace culture, and the particular social structures present (Yang, Steinfeld, and Zimmerman 2019).

To do so, designers can address challenges by implementing value-sensitive and user-centred design principles to guide the development of such clinical AI. Value-sensitive design accounts for human values throughout the design process, allowing developers to translate a set of values into system requirements (Abrams, Maloney-Krichmar, and Preece 2004; Friedman et al. 2013). Here, the values of interest are the *embedded* values, or “values that have been intentionally, and successfully, embedded in an AI system by its designers” (van de Poel 2020). For example, value-sensitive

design can be used to introduce requirements that translate the values promoted by the European Union guidelines for trustworthy AI (Lemonne 2018; HLEG 2020), such as transparency and explainability. In the case of AIs that predict patient preferences, relevant values would include respect for patient autonomy, nonmaleficence, preservation of clinician agency, promotion of shared decision-making, timeliness, and commitment to providing goal concordant care. The translation of values in a set of compatible system requirements can be facilitated by using structured questionnaires and design workshops involving clinicians, surrogates, and, possibly, patients enrolled from retrospective studies (see Section 3.2.5).

What is a good system design? Finally, user-centred design offers the possibility of developing systems based on the characteristics and tasks of their users (Brunner et al. 2017). Designers should leverage user-centred design of clinical AIs to ensure high degrees of usability and robustness, considering different interfaces (e.g., tablets, computer monitors, interactive screens); the particularities of the clinicians' working schedule; clinicians' comfort with technology; and the characteristics of the location for the consultation with surrogates. Moreover, if AI is actively used with surrogates (see Section 3.2.4), the display of patient information and treatment predictions should allow the assessment of the system trustworthiness by heterogeneous populations of stakeholders with diverse languages and belief-systems. Therefore, designers should consider multilingual interfaces, using vocal support functionalities or simplified content and interactions in the case of specific impairments among surrogates. Finally, the integration of AI into clinical workflows should support timely decision-making and the collection of patient data after the choice of treatment, such as in the case of retrospective studies (see Section 3.2.5).

3.2.4 Deployment

Integration into clinical shared decision-making. Another key consideration is how a decision-making process involving clinicians, surrogates, and AI might unfold. On the one hand, AI may be implemented in a workflow to provide predictions only to clinicians. As a pilot study has shown, health care professionals may be quite open to the use of AI for helping them understand what treatment a patient would have wanted (Biller-Andorno et al. 2021). In this scenario, surrogates would not be presented with an algorithmic prediction of preferred treatments but, rather, with a suggestion by a “clinicians+AI” dyad (Ferrario and Loi 2022). Similar to the “Modeling” step, explainability methods would support clinicians in forming a mental model of the AI prediction to then take into account its suggestion as part of their⁹ preparation for consulting with surrogates. Clinicians would need to be instructed in supporting inference processes by presenting the AI predictions to surrogates and providing them with explanations. An AI-based decision-support designed primarily for clinician use may also be especially useful when no surrogates are available or surrogates are unable or unwilling to assume their role.

In another scenario, both clinicians and surrogates could consult the AI and its predictions, either individually or in a joint process. Surrogates would be given the possibility to interact with the AI to improve their understanding of its prediction through explanations that might at the same time foster their trust in the system. Recent

⁹ Although the provision of epistemic guarantees is considered to be necessary to hold *justified* beliefs on the trustworthiness of an AI (Durán and Jongsma 2021), the nature of these guarantees is currently under discussion. Specifically, it is not clear whether explainability methods are an example of such guarantees (Durán and Jongsma 2021; Ferrario and Loi 2022).

empirical evidence supports this possibility, suggesting that surrogates may respond positively to the support of an AI to predict the preferences of their loved ones. (Howard et al. 2021). Surrogates may benefit from having a guide in the deliberation process and feel less isolated in decision-making; however, AI should be limited to the role of a support tool, since surrogates rightly emphasize that they have the responsibility and authority to decide which treatments be considered for their loved ones (Howard et al. 2021).

One concern is that surrogates may disagree with the AI and its predictions, perceiving the AI as challenging their decision-making or undermining their confidence. (Rid and Wendler 2014a). Potential conflict between surrogates and an AI tool would undermine the key hypothesis that “if a[n] [AI] can accurately predict patient treatment preferences, it also may reduce surrogate distress” (Wendler et al. 2016). Therefore, conflicts arise when accurate predictions on historical data¹⁰ are not *sufficient* for the surrogates to trust the AI prediction, leading, arguably, to surrogates’ stress in decision-making. In summary, surrogates may approve of having a guide in the form of an AI patient preference predictor, and this support may improve efforts to provide goal concordant goal (Howard et al. 2021). However, outcomes perceived as surprising,

¹⁰ Accuracy is a property of an AI that is measured on a given dataset during a performance evaluation of the system. It refers to a performance on historical data and cannot be computed for a given prediction. Therefore, expressions such as “the PPP increases surrogates’ predictive accuracy” (Howard et al. 2021) and cognates refer to a standard that is achieved *before* decision-making in clinical practice. As a result, *during* decision-making, accuracy may support surrogates in assessing the trustworthiness of the AI.

puzzling, or incorrect may still result in discord. Such conflict may undermine the value of using the AI in clinical practice (Rid and Wendler 2014a).

This said, we argue that the emergence of conflicts between surrogates and an AI patient preference predictor is to be managed, not pre-emptively avoided. Conflicts can also emerge between surrogates and clinicians when clinicians have a position on what is in the patient's best interest. In this case, disagreements are often resolved through consultation—possibly involving a clinical ethicist—and discussion of the different options at stake. Similarly, we argue, when there is disagreement with a suggestion generated by AI, it becomes relevant to support understanding of what underlies the AI prediction, creating space to reflect on potential biases while minimizing distress from lack of appropriate information, inadequate explanations, or inefficient communication.

We believe it remains an open question for now which scenarios of AI-assisted decision-making are ethically sound to implement: should such AI be reserved for aiding clinician decision making or is there a potential application for direct use by surrogates? Although the literature agrees on the supporting role of an AI predicting patient preferences (Rid and Wendler 2010; Biller-Andorno et al. 2021; Howard et al. 2021; S. D. Halpern 2018), it is not yet clear who should draw on its predictions, at what point, and why. We argue that, at the time of writing, more empirical research is needed to better understand the interactions of surrogates, clinicians, and such an AI system. However, in general, we think access should be provided to both clinicians and surrogates with due explanations and only as desired. Also, the AI-assisted decision-making process may benefit from professional moderation through a clinical ethics consultant, particularly if surrogates are uncomfortable with the AI suggestions. Should AI-assisted decision-making in the future prove to be vastly superior to unaided

decision-making and become the gold standard, the voluntariness of its use by healthcare professional might need to be revisited. In that case, AI might hold an assumed role as quasi-surrogate, and patients would need to explicitly state in an advance directive their preference to decline its use.

3.2.5 Evaluation

Performance evaluation: goal concordant care. Retrospective agreement studies offer the possibility of testing the performance of such AI in supporting goal concordant care. This performance validation process makes use of qualitative and quantitative metrics (Markus, Kors, and Rijnbeek 2021) and is grounded by studies set in realistic settings (Doshi-Velez and Kim 2017) as opposed to the validation in the “Modeling” step.

Considering the ICU use case again, two distinct types of retrospective studies can be used to evaluate performance of the AI. In the first study, the predictions computed at relevant ICU decision-making moments may be compared to the decisions made by clinicians for a sample of patients following discharge. This would minimize risk during the training phase by presenting clinicians with the AI predictions only after patients are discharged. Clinicians could then review all cases by means of the patient charts, describing their decision-making processes (with or without surrogate decision-makers, available ADs etc.), and comparing their outcomes with the preferences predicted by the clinical AI at each selected decision-making moment. This type of study evaluates the rationale behind the clinical AI predictions as compared to the one of the clinicians. It could be run when the AI is newly deployed in the clinical workflow, or periodically to monitor the accuracy of the system, or to train clinicians in AI-assisted decision-making on selected ethically sensitive patient cases.

A second type of retrospective study may involve patients and their relatives (or legal guardians) in a period six to twelve months following discharge from the ICU. Questionnaires and structured phone interviews could explore and quantify the extent of retrospective agreement to intensive care, which is the stated approval of the applied treatments, depending on functional outcome as measured by e.g., the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) and patient satisfaction (Kiphuth et al. 2010). Then, to assess AI performance, one could analyze how functional outcome and satisfaction influence retrospective agreement to intensive care qualitatively and identify predisposing factors (e.g., demographic and clinical data, such as preadmission mRS) for retrospective agreement to intensive care (Kiphuth et al. 2010). This type of study may allow comparing the decisions that the AI suggested with those that have been made for all patients. As a result, one could analyze for which cases, following the AI predictions, it would have resulted in higher rates of retrospective agreement to intensive care, as well as satisfaction.

These evaluations of the AI would contribute to a better understanding of the potential of these systems to foster goal-concordant care, providing a degree of protection against violations of patient autonomy, avoiding preference misdiagnoses (Mulley, Trimble, and Elwyn 2012) and pro-intervention treatment biases that may not correspond with patients' interests.

Performative prediction. Data generated in the retrospective studies can be collected and used for the modeling of the (updated) ML models predicting patients' preferred treatments. To do so, the personal-level information, the preferred treatments, and the feedback from the interviews of patients following an ICU stay can be added to the existing database (or overwrite existing data points). Therefore, the deployment of an AI predicting patient preferences allows new data to be generated via retrospective

studies and these data, in turn, affect the update procedures of the AI, namely the retraining of the ML models that predict the preferred treatments. This phenomenon is an example of “performative prediction”, i.e., the occurrence of a shift in the distribution of patients’ data that results from the deployment of a ML model (Perdomo et al. 2020). Performative prediction breaks the common assumption in ML modeling that data distributions are somehow static or that their change over time depends on exogenous causes—such as a pandemic—providing an *endogenous cause* for the shift of the patient data distribution: the deployment and use of ML models to assist decision-making.

As a result, if an AI to predict patient preferences is incorporated into use, designers have to acknowledge that the choice of which patients to interview in retrospective studies, how to proceed with data collection, and the methods of analysis of their data all potentially introduce bias¹¹ that affects the “Data Collection” and “Modeling” steps due to performative prediction. In particular, this process may contribute to reinforce class imbalance (see Section 3.2.1). Management of this occurrence suggests that the sampling strategies and experimental protocols of retrospective studies become part of the documentation supporting the transparency of the AI system and its maintenance.

¹¹ This bias may manifest, for example, in collecting data mostly from patients who survived at after discharge or from those with low levels of cognitive deficit, so they can actively participate in the study.

Life Cycle Steps	Challenges	Recommendations
Data Collection	1. <i>Collecting treatment scenarios</i>	1. Collect treatments and outcomes letting responders indicate preferred likelihoods and durations of post-intervention health states
	2. <i>Bias in future-self forecasting</i>	2. Development of digital tools to manage bias in future-self forecasting using narratives
Modeling	1. <i>Multiplicity in modeling</i>	1. Remove low-performance ML models, aggregate “contiguous” treatment scenarios, possibly refining “Data Collection”
	2. <i>Technical bias and transparency</i>	2. Endorse transparency frameworks that include technical bias emerging during “Modeling”
	3. <i>Explainability in modeling</i>	3. Use explainability methods to assess feature importance (e.g., SHAPley values) and explain treatment predictions (e.g., counterfactuals)
	4. <i>Performance evaluation: AI vs. surrogates</i>	4. Use the AI vs. surrogates performance evaluation as prima facie evidence of the AI accuracy over different treatment scenarios, only. Refine “Data Collection” following the outcomes of the evaluation
System Design	1. <i>Embedding values in system design</i>	1. Use value-sensitive design (“embedded values”) to guide design of the AI system and define its requirements
	2. <i>What is a good system design?</i>	2. Use user-centered design to ensure appropriate levels of user experience, usability, the timely use of the AI predictions, and its appropriate integration in clinical workflows
Deployment	1. <i>Integration into clinical shared decision-making</i>	1.1 Design different integration scenarios for the AI to predict preferences
		1.2 Integrate different strategies of resolution (e.g. including clinical ethicist) for disagreements
		1.3 Train clinicians in structuring discussions on patient’s preferred treatments, providing emotional support and emphasizing shared decision-making
Evaluation	1. <i>Performance evaluation: goal concordant care</i>	1. Performance evaluations in different retrospective studies (with clinicians and discharged patients) to measure retrospective agreement
	2. <i>Performative prediction</i>	2. Manage the bias induced by performative prediction and affecting “Data Collection” via retrospective studies

Figure 2. The steps of the AI system life cycle, their challenges and our recommendations.

Conclusions

The integration into clinical practice of algorithms that predict care preferences, particularly when involving advanced AI, is a complex and interdisciplinary exercise that draws on ethicists, computer scientists, designers, clinicians, surrogates, and patients. In this work, we have proposed a new approach to organize this endeavour, suggesting actionable recommendations to hopefully fill a gap that has persisted since the early days of proposed patient preference prediction. At the basis of our approach lies the conviction that the interdisciplinary nature of all stages of the design of AIs to predict patient preferences should be harnessed yet organized appropriately, moving beyond taking either theoretical or pragmatic questions in isolation. To do so, we have proposed to consider AIs as socio-technical systems, considering their life cycle as a guide for our discussions. This theory-driven yet application-oriented approach has allowed us to discuss existing and new challenges for implementation of AI preference

predictors into clinical workflows. Hopefully, our attempt will ignite a critical discussion on how to best shape the use, evaluation, and continuous improvement of algorithms assisting ethically challenging decisions in clinical practice.

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